

Complex compounds of ions with d^{6-10} electronic configuration with bidentate heterocyclic ligands (N, S)

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Some new complexes of Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} have been synthesized with bidentate heterocyclic ligand (N, S) of the dibenzofuran series. The complexes were characterized by chemical analyses, UV, visible, IR, EPR and NMR spectral analyses, conductivity and magnetic susceptibility measurements. A sulfur and a nitrogen atoms of the ligand are involved in the coordination to the metal.

During the last years, the coordination chemistry has been considerably enriched due to synthesis and characterization of a large number of four-coordinate square-planar complexes of transition elements in which the metal is coordinated by sulfur. In some of our previous works¹ theoretical considerations of the behaviour of sulfur as a donor have been presented. It results from these papers that the heavier donor atoms, including sulfur, exhibit vacant "d" orbitals, able to accept "d" electrons of the metal ion, forming $d\pi-d\pi$ bonds. Particular attention in this area has been paid to the complex compounds formed by transition metals with thioamides, that act as bidentate ligands, using both sulfur and nitrogen as donor atoms².

The purpose of the present work is the structure of some new complexes of ions with d^{6-10} electronic configuration : Fe^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with bidentate heterocyclic ligand (N, S), the thioamide 3-(2'-thiofuroilamino) dibenzofuran (TFADBF)³, by taking into account the results of elemental analyses, UV, visible, IR, EPR and NMR spectral analyses, conductivity and magnetic susceptibility measurements.

Results and discussion

The complexes obtained were microcrystalline coloured powders, whose melting points are higher than of the pure

thioamide. They are stable at RT and their molar conductivities showed that all the complexes are non-electrolytes with $\lambda = 0.88-1.97 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ in DMF ($10^{-4} M$) solutions at RT (Table 1).

Table 1. Analytical and physico-chemical data of complexes*

Compd.	Colour	M.p. °C	Mol. cond. ^a Ω^{-1} $\text{cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$	μ_{eff} B.M.	Metal(%) Found/(Calcd.)
[FeLCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	Red	168	1.97	4.86	12.75/(12.52)
[CoLCl ₂]	Red	182	0.88	2.20	13.58/(13.93)
[NiLCl ₂]	Brown	154	1.29	Diamag.	13.41/(13.88)
[CuLCl ₂]	Orange	139	1.54	1.92	14.69/(14.85)
[ZnLCl ₂]	Yellow	148	1.93	Diamag.	15.07/(15.23)
[CdLCl ₂]	Brown	163	1.08	Diamag.	23.73/(23.60)
[HgLCl ₂]	Yellow	175	1.32	Diamag.	35.84/(35.52)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, S, N and H analyses; ^a $10^{-4} M$ DMF solution, 22°.

In literature⁴ it is stated that thioamide form a complex vibrational group. A comparative interpretation of the IR spectral data (Table 2) suggests that TFADBF act as a bidentate ligand in the investigated complex compounds, using both sulfur and nitrogen as donor atoms.

The ligand bands at 3220, 3060 and 1600 cm^{-1} characteristic for ν_{NH_2} and δ_{NH_2} , appear in complexes at lower frequencies and more flattened. These changes indicate the coordination of the nitrogen with the metal ions. The position of the thioamide band I ($\nu(\text{C-N}) + \delta(\text{C-H})$) at 1460 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand is not shifted appreciably

Table 2. IR bands (cm^{-1}) of TFADBF and its complexes

TFADBF	[FeLCl ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]	[CoLCl ₂]	[NiLCl ₂]	[CuLCl ₂]	[ZnLCl ₂]	[CdLCl ₂]	[HgLCl ₂]	Assignment
-	3448	-	-	-	-	-	-	ν_{OH} water
3220	3218	3204	3200	3208	3210	3200	3206	ν_{NH_2}
3060	3055	3010	3000	3028	2997	2980	3012	ν_{NH}
2900	2880	2875	2890	2888	2847	2852	2896	$\nu_{\text{C-H}}$
1600	1580	1605	1598	1610	1607	1590	1604	δ_{NH_2}
1460	1475	1468	1466	1472	1462	1470	1460	Thioamide band I
1360	1390	1405	1398	1395	1400	1410	1408	Thioamide band II
1210	1200	1205	1200	1215	1200	1202	1204	Thioamide band III
-	890	-	-	-	-	-	-	Coordinated water
740	720	722	715	710	718	722	708	Thioamide band IV
-	465	475	468	470	458	463	472	$\nu_{\text{M-N}}$

in the spectra of the complexes, while the position of thioamide band II ($\nu(\text{C-N}) + \delta(\text{C-H}) + \nu(\text{C=S})$) of ligand (1360 cm^{-1}) suffered a considerable shift towards higher wavenumber side in the complexes ($1390\text{--}1410 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The thioamide band III ($\nu(\text{C-N}) + \nu(\text{C=S})$) at 1210 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand is not shifted in the spectra of the complexes and the thioamide band IV ($\nu_s(\text{C=S}) + \nu_{\text{as}}(\text{C=S})$) from 740 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the ligand is shifted to lower wavenumber side in its complexes. These changes confirmed that the sulphur participates in bonding to the metal ion. The metal complexes are also characterized by the appearance of some new bands of medium and low intensity at $460\text{--}420 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which can be assigned to $\nu(\text{M-N})$ stretching frequencies⁵. A band due to coordinated water appears in the spectrum of the Fe^{II} complex around 890 cm^{-1} and 3500 cm^{-1} .

The magnetic moment value of [Fe(TFADBF)Cl₂(H₂O)₂] is 4.86 B.M. which indicates that the complex is spin-free and it has octahedral geometry. The electronic spectrum shows a broad absorption band at 16600 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned to the $^5T_{2g} \rightarrow ^5E_g$ transition⁶.

For [Co(TFADBF)Cl₂], the magnetic moment values is 2.20 B.M. and its electronic spectrum displays two bands, at 16840 and 21580 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned to the $^2A_{1g} \rightarrow ^2B_{2g}$ and $^2A_{1g} \rightarrow ^2E_g$ transitions, respectively, in a square-planar configuration⁶.

As far as [Ni(TFADBF)Cl₂] is concerned, it appears to be diamagnetic. Its electronic spectrum exhibits four bands, at 21250 , 30333 , 33456 and 38280 cm^{-1} . The first and the second band are of low intensity, being purely $d-d$ transi-

tions, assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1A_{2g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{2g}$ transitions, respectively. The third band is developed by a strong charge transfer transition, while the fourth one is due to interligand interactions ($\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$). These results also suggest a square-planar configuration around the transition metal ion⁷.

The RT magnetic moment value is 1.92 B.M. for [Cu(TFADBF)Cl₂] indicating the presence of one free electron. The electronic spectrum displays three spectral bands, at 14470 , 20620 and 26480 cm^{-1} . The first band corresponds to the $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2A_{1g}$ transition and the second one to the $^2B_{1g} \rightarrow ^2E_g$ transition, the third band being assigned to a charge transfer transition. All these observations lead to the conclusion that the geometry is also square-planar⁶. The compound [Cu(TFADBF)Cl₂] offer a very intense EPR spectrum, with anisotropic parameters $g_{\parallel} = 2.2404$ and $g_{\perp} = 2.0704$, in agreement with the d^9 electronic configuration for Cu^{II} in this square-planar complex compound⁸.

The absorption bands appearing in the UV domain are considered to be characteristic of the ligand. The assignment of $n \rightarrow \pi$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions as being due to the (C=S) bond was made based on Sandstrom's investigations⁹. The UV electronic spectra of [Zn(TFADBF)Cl₂], [Cd(TFADBF)Cl₂] and [Hg(TFADBF)Cl₂] show the occurrence of an absorption characteristic of $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition shifted by hypsochromic effect. The ¹³C NMR spectrum of the free ligand shows a signal at $\delta = 195.2$ ppm due to the carbon atom from the C=S group. In the spectra of its complex compounds with Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}, the signal appears at lower values of the magnetic field ($189\text{--}191$ ppm)

proving the involvement of the sulfur atom in the coordination. The ^1H NMR spectrum shows a signal at $\delta = 12.24$ ppm corresponding to the proton in the imido (-NH) group. It appears 0.2–0.7 ppm shifted in the spectra of the complex compounds, indicating the involvement of the nitrogen atom in the coordination. Therefore, the coordinative δ bands are due to the sulfur and nitrogen atoms in the thioamidic group.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade: $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Fluka A.G.p.a.), $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck p.a.), $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck p.a.), $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck p.a.), ZnCl_2 (B.D.H. p.a.), CdCl_2 (B.D.H. p.a.), HgCl_2 (Merck p.a.), TFADBF (double recrystallized).

The IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer FT-1600 Hewlett Packard instrument in anhyd. KBr pellets. The electronic spectra were obtained in 10^{-3} M acetone solutions, with an Unicam UV 2-300 spectrophotometer. X-band EPR spectra were recorded in powder form at RT on an Art-5-Ifin spectrometer, the modulation of magnetic field being 100 KHz, using Mn^{2+} as an internal standard. Both ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a Varion Gemini 300 B.B. The molar conductivities were measured by using OK-102 conductivity meter at 22° . The magnetic susceptibility measurements were performed on a Gouy balance at RT.

Preparation of the complexes : 0.02 M Thioamide (TFADBF) in ethanol solution was added (dropwise with continuous stirring) to an ethanolic or aqueous solution of

the metal chloride (0.02 M) in a 1 : 1 molar ratio. The mixture was gently stirred for one hour, and then left at RT for three hours. The precipitated metal complexes were washed with ethanol and diethyl ether and finally dried under reduced pressure.

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